

FORECASTING OF COLOURS IN CREATIVE COMPOSITION OF TEXTILE FABRIC AND FASHION

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Colour is the most enriched and endless form of human life. It reflects our mood and more importantly, it has more influence and effect on our lives than we realize. How can we define colour, a reality, a feeling that creates energy, enthusiasm, potential, anger, affection, passion and many other feelings in us. If we are in pleasant feeling, colour fills us with the feel of joy and happiness and in contrary to this if we are unhappy and sad the colours are there, who fill with the feel of unhealthy, unhappiness and sadness. Now it is a matter to think upon that why we correlate our feelings with colour or how colour reflects our mood or our internal expressions in a physical manner. It is not only because of colour but of course because of its composition too. We always look for a new colour palette range or a new invention but have we ever thought that from where did colours come and why they show their impact on us and our lives. Craving for colour, forces human to create invent and generate inventions, of course a human with artistic or creative brain and heart, who not only evolve in engraving of colours but also put efforts in to it to foster. A new innovation of colour means an exploration of colour, technology, culture and positive or negative impact on social psychological, physical life too. Often we use our personal choices to colour selection and it is influenced by inherited habits and culture. All colours have different – different impacts to others for example for common person a banana is of yellow colour while at the other hand of extreme it may be a colour of expressing emotion for a painter and so on the other colours too. If an external beauty whether it is a painting, a sculpture, a home, a dress or any place, if it is not explained with a sublime way, it is untrustworthy or a failure of composition. Colour is the most important element of any composition and similarly a composition means meticulously selecting what elements will appear in the picture and then placing them carefully in the frame to create a balanced and interesting organization. A composition is to accumulate the small - small units or elements, so the entire beauty of that composition will come to its best way of presentation. In other words, a composition is the way in which all elements and components work together to form a coherent whole. Composition is an important part of art, which is compelled to be use where new creation or invention is needed, and to create a composition, focal point view, perspective, rhythm, proportion, colour selection everything is essential. It totally depends upon the person's personal choice that what he or she wants to show as his or her expression in composition and this is also true that everybody looks for its own preferable colour combinations but yes if there is a creative piece, it is not necessary that it will be depending on the creator's mood but it will reflect and explain the language of that creative composition, that what it wants to tell to others. Composition is not restricted to create only in paintings, sculptures and home decor but it is a sign of the thought that is shown by its creator whether it is any form, a dress, a textile fabric piece or a book. Yes! Even a book can be composite in a creative way. Colour forecasting is considered as one of the remarkable driving forces for textile fabric and fashion and so as to with the other arts

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too. Now how colour forecasting works for its composition, it is depending on the circumstances, weather, and social effectiveness, physical and psychological aspects? Whatever but the little information exist about its area of study and even lesser in depth information is currently available about this complex and instinctive process. When a keen desired mind plans to satisfy its soul through a creation of composition in any art field, colours play a very important role on that and to proof the focus, selection of colour or forecasting of colours is actually not only one of the main parts of it but also helps others to achieve that level of thought to understand the composition. There is no one who can determines the trend of colour according to the composition but only the composer or the mind, heart and soul of the creator who creates that, hence it is very needed that the inventor who composes its composition, should have the vital knowledge and strongly dedicated feeling towards its composition and colour preferences. Of the many ways in which we choose to express ourselves. The colour and its composition probably makes the most immediate and powerful impact. Colour can be magical and once you start playing with it there will be no stopping you.

Textiles are defined as the yarns that are woven or knitted to make fabrics and it has such an important bearing on our daily lives that everybody needs to know something about them. The use of textiles links the myriad cultures of the world and defines the way they clothe themselves, adorn their surroundings and go about their lives. Textiles have been an integral part of human daily life for thousands of years, with the first use of textiles more likely felt, dates back to the late stone age and Palaeolithic age roughly 1,00,000 years ago. However the earliest instances of cotton, silk, and linen begin to appear around 5,000 BC in India, Egypt and China and there of weaving with different colour combinations from the Byzantine period. People have used textiles to cover them in various senses like for warmth, covering, personal and social wealth etc. Since that time, as our cultural, economical, physical social, psychological and industrial each aspect developed and so of with the colour variations, which is remarkably increasing day by day. Organising a creative composition is exactly starting with reference material and it can be anything a palm tree leaf, a tier or wheel, a lady, a child, a garden view a scenery etc. but to manage it is an effective manner and a way of expression in a fabric, some technical methodology with the accumulated data and an accurate blending of colours, thus the result is a fantastic and revolutionary output or product. Before the experiment goes on, decision associates with selection, choice of subject matter and finishing with necessary details and touches of colour insured the unity and impact of the product of fabric. Basic design principles introduce with a focus how professional designers create saleable textile and fashion product for different variety of customer. Various lectures, weekly meetings and many researches explore the trend of colours, fashion and design in fabric influenced by social, economical and historical views too.

Colour forecasting combine theories and histories of previously collected data of fashion, trend and pattern design with process of organizing and analysing and synthesizing the data in to an actionable forecast. A creative and experimental composition in the form of fabric is based on the forecaster accumulated data, observations, multiple view of customers, emerging trends and colours and product psychological view, styling and many other research categories, for example we can take IKAT fabric of Indonesia, India and central Asia.

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It is made by weaving of dyed threads and mainly in the warp threads of weaving. Now the things is IKAT is worldwide famous for its rare and experimental appearance of pattern design making and variety of colours with different colour combinations , so there is a great challenge for a designer or composer who will take a change to make it differently with a variety of colour effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

Hence it can be clearly said that colour is not physical property of shapes but also the resultant of social, psychological, economical aspects rather than a phenomenon of perception too. Colour is not only restricted to any particular art form but it has widely accepted area in our day to day life in every aspect and manner and so as to with fashion and textiles too, because what we wear and what is our social shade in our surroundings is a deep sense of our persona at our outlook too.

REFERENCES:

- 1 *Textiles: fiber to fabric* by Bernard P. Corbman
- 2 *Finding fabrics* by Akshay Tholia
- 3 *Design and colour* by Michelle Scragg with Robin Capon
- 4 *Color* by Barron's
- 5 *Encyclopaedia and Wikipedia*